

Podcasts: A Cutting-Edge Approach to Education

Parthiva Sinha, M A (Pursuing), Department of English Literature, Bankura Sammilani College, West Bengal

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Abstract

Every industry is impacted by technology, and edification is no different. The way we distribute edification is transmuting as a result of incipient technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning that have already made their way into the sector. With the utilization of artificial intelligence, we have been able to make learning more engaging and efficacious for students. Inculcation and learning are becoming increasingly individualized thanks to AI-powered systems that can identify a student's learning style and acclimate edifications to their desiderata. India has a growing number of individuals who are connected to the cyber world, with an immensely colossal chunk of its population having access to the cyber world and having smartphones. Podcasts have developed groups of like-minded people, given listeners a sense of community, and provided a venue for interaction and the sharing of interests. India has always been voluminous in audio listening, dating back to the Prasar Bharti days. The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 goal is focused on the utilization and integration of technology. In many instances, audio podcasts and video lectures together improved student performance. The integration of podcasting into the landscape of scholarly communication demonstrates that there are more aspects of podcasting to

be studied than just how it is generating new types of audio storytelling. Instead, podcasting has the power to change not only what we learn but also how academics approach their work. Pratham, India's leading NGO in the space of elementary education, has been playing an active role during this pandemic to connect with students and communities across the country and partner with governments to support learning. Indian universities need to offer a model of learning and teaching that is ever more advanced, with authentic assessments, personal lifetime learning, and face-to-face delivery combined with technology. India should adopt more creative measures to guarantee that all kids have access to education during any pandemic-like situation. E-learning practices should continue to benefit pupils greatly, and podcasts can be of great use along with other options.

Keywords: Podcast, Podcasting, RSS, NEP, Prasar Bharti, Pratham etc.

Over the years, technological advancement has occurred incredibly expeditiously. Due to never-ending developments, there are more and more internet applications. One of the most

inventive developments in information technology was the revelation of podcasts.

The newest on-the-go, on-demand technology is podcasting. A podcast is essentially a digitally recorded piece of audio or web/visual content that is made available online for downloading to a computer or MP3 player. Podcasting provides many more possibilities in terms of material and programming than radio does, similar to radio on demand. The nicest part of podcasting is that you can download and listen to any program you want whenever and wherever you want. The fundamental draw of podcasting is the flexibility to listen from anywhere, at any time. The most popular file types for podcasting are audio or video, however, any file type, including photos and PDF, can be used.

An essential aspect of podcasts is that, in contrast to blogs and wikis, which may only contain written content, their voice gives digital resources a more personal appearance. To make interaction actual and to improve speaking and listening abilities that enable you to connect and communicate with others in real life, it is crucial to integrate all of these many online tools.

Definitions Given By Researchers

In 2004, journalist Ben Hammersley coined the denomination "podcast" as a coalescence of the words "broadcast" and "iPod," a then-recent Apple product that sanctioned users to download MP3 audio files and heedfully aurally perceive them on-the-go. Most early

podcasts were drawn from radio programs. Albeit there is dissatisfaction with the term, it perpetuates to be utilized. Both moieties of this portmanteau are inopportune for the modern form of the medium, which is neither constrained by radio conventions nor heedfully auricular discerned on iPods.

Podcasting, according to Meng, is the process of recording an audio event, song, voice, or combination of sounds and uploading that digital sound object to a website or blog in an RSS 2.0 envelope (or feed). Users can subscribe to a Web page containing RSS 2.0 tagged audio files on selected Web pages and have these files automatically download into an audio management program on their personal computer using specialized news readers. The podcasts are instantly transmitted to the user's portable audio device when they synchronize it with their personal computer so they can be listened to whenever and wherever is most convenient for them.

The early media definition of podcasts was based on the file format and method of distribution rather than on radio or iPods. Podcasts were first an offshoot of RSS, a web feed that visitors to post-based websites, like blogs, could subscribe to for consistent updates. As opposed to the algorithmically driven feeds that characterize the majority of modern social media sites, users could curate many feeds on a single feed aggregator like the now-defunct Google Reader. Initially, RSS feeds were text-only, but in 2000, developers started experimenting with adding audio and video files to feeds, giving rise to the

idea of the "audioblog." (Wikipedia contributors)

Vogele and Gard distinguished three types of podcasting: class podcasts, which are defined by their participation in any learning process within a course;

Podcasting Devices

administrative podcasts, which are used to disseminate things like general information, rules, and guidelines; special events podcasts, which broadcast lessons from guest lecturers, conferences, awards, and honours.

A podcast can be summarized as a collection of audio or video files that can be downloaded on the internet via a procedure known as syndication. The distributor's server releases the media files referred to as web feeds in batches. A pod catcher is specialized software that clients use to access media files that are available online. The producer and up loader of media files and other content for web feeds is in charge

of doing so. It takes a lot of concentration and attention to produce podcasts because the procedure is quite complicated. The podcast is first created, and then it is released. The hardest stage to complete is the recording stage, and three essential recording tools are required for effective recording. Software for recording, a microphone, and headphones are the three items. To convey the audio noises to the

mixing device, a decent microphone is required. In order to properly set the mixing device, headphones are crucial for monitoring recording levels. Typically, the default sample format is 16 bits. A copy of the file is often made after recording but before editing. The microphone should be chosen on the mixing unit as the primary input choice. Using the microphone, volume adjustments are made on the mixer.

The system is deemed suitable for podcasting after the volume has been properly set. Publishing is the last step in the podcast creation process. The distributor must then transmit the podcast to listeners after it has been recorded. For any user to have access to the podcasts, they must subscribe to RSS feeds. The listener can receive automatic podcasts from the distributor using aggregators like iTunes. To construct blogs, software like WordPress is utilized. For any user to have access to the podcasts, they must subscribe to RSS feeds. The listener can receive automatic podcasts from the distributor using aggregators like iTunes. RSS feeds are easier to create using blog software like Word Press. The user, also known as the listener, is now able to access the podcast files relatively quickly following the recording and publishing processes. If there is a new episode, the distributor repeats the procedure, and the cycle is complete.

Podcasts are a novel type of digital text that calls for fresh approaches to analysis based on knowledge of the politics, affordances, and history of the medium. Initially conceived as an accessible medium for novice creators, an audio version of the

blog, podcasts emerged at the nexus of RSS (Really Simple Syndication) and digital audio technology. The early technical difficulties of creating and downloading podcasts tended to favour the same group as tech culture (white men), but as affordable recording technology has continued to advance and there are fewer industry restrictions, podcasting has grown quickly. In 2021, Apple reported that there were 2 million podcasts available.

Podcasts and Academia

Education is one of the top categories among the thousands of podcasts that are active and frequently release new episodes. The goal of podcasts created for students is to make studying for tests as simple and painless as possible. While those studying podcast genres are more interested in examining how podcasting has created a space for new forms of sound-based storytelling, media studies scholars are more interested in questions of what defines podcasting and whether a shift away from RSS technology to platform-exclusive shows is signaling the end of the medium's golden age. Scholars have started to theorize podcasting through the act of generating podcasts itself, while the most developed area of podcast research centers on the use of podcasts for pedagogy. The introduction of podcasting into the realm of scholarly communication illustrates how the study of podcasting has the potential to alter both what and how scholars conduct their research.

There is a wide range of academic interest in podcasting. A fast search for academic work currently yields more

results from researchers in education, but some early work came from what we might roughly refer to as "media and cultural studies." These academicians contend that podcasting can be acclimated to present instructional material to students in novel and fascinating ways. Podcasts enable researchers to share their work, provide on-demand lectures through MOOCs, or allow students to review difficult lectures and take more thorough notes. Academics that enjoy listening to podcasts are interested in them, as are media researchers and those working in the field of digital media. Even though each study may come to a different conclusion; the fact that they are interested in the same area justifies working together under the same banner. (Berry)

Types of Educational Podcasts:

Any podcast whose main goal is to educate its listeners qualifies as an educational podcast. An entire episode of an instructional podcast could be devoted to discussing a single idea or period of history. Some educational podcasts use an instructional style with the goal of providing their listeners with specific skills that can be used in particular situations. Others gain a following due to the fascinating personalities of their hosts, whose voices are enjoyable to listen to and who have the skill to transform even the most uninteresting topics into something that is impossible to halt while listening to. The following categories apply to educational podcasts based on their participation and content.

- **Lecture podcasts-** They are recordings of either previously recorded or live lectures. It can be difficult to turn a live lecture into a

podcast because the audio quality might be subpar and it might completely or just mention slides. It can be preferable to record a single monologue created just for a podcast lesson.

- **Supplementary podcasts-** They are made to supplement already-existing lectures and learning resources and to offer more in-depth or extended analysis of a subject. These may be created by the instructors of the courses, or students may be led to other pertinent internet podcasts.
- **Integrated podcasts-** They are especially helpful as supplemental content because they adopt the conversational format of two or more participants. This might be a roundtable conversation with experts from various fields as participants. Investigate the abundance of podcasts that are accessible online from academic units and cross-institutional partnerships who use this format to present their research; you could find some that are pertinent to your course. Integrated podcasts can be created in-house by bringing in coworkers, collaborators, and guests to record conversations. The majority of academics like discussing their fields of study, and with little forward planning, recordings of these beneficial talks can give students fresh or alternative perspectives on the debates taking place in their fields of study.

Students are especially fond of this engaging yet casual discussion approach that integrates the characteristics of the participants.

- **Summary podcasts-** They can also be used to summarise a lecture or a particular subject of study's main ideas.
- **Primer podcasts-** They can be used to provide feedback or to get pupils ready for upcoming lessons and tests. A primer podcast will introduce a new subject of study, as opposed to a summary podcast that could "wrap up" the week.
- **Student podcasts-** They may be applied as tests or assignments. One approach is to give students the task of conducting research for and producing a podcast as a group project. Group work is notoriously difficult to incorporate in online learning.

Some Popular Educational Podcasts

The popular scientist Brian Cox and comedian Robin Ince's program *The Infinite Monkey Cage* is both entertaining and educational. After the academic misery of studying organic chemistry in school, Brian Cox has a completely different method that might make it even simpler for people who haven't had to think about science to get started. Before he became a professor of particle physics, Cox played keyboards for two British bands, but it's not his musical background that makes him a rock star. He is well-known in the UK for using the media to make science more approachable, together with Carl Sagan and

David Attenborough. Four panel guests are typically present in each episode, three of whom are typically scientists with knowledge of the day's topic and one of whom is a comedian. This is one of the best scientific podcasts available because of the rare combination of comedians and scientists. Robin Ince, a British comedian, offers the perfect humorous foil to the nerdy, physics-obsessed Cox. Ince and the guest comedian frequently take on the role of a funny audience substitute by posing questions that regular people could ask which prevents the program from turning into a jargon-heavy academic discussion.

Vox is known for breaking down complex concepts into simple terms, but its newest podcast, *Unexplainable*, twists that notion on its head. *Unexplainable* doesn't help to demystify the everyday barrage of knowledge; instead, it surrounds us with history's most puzzling mysteries. *Unexplainable* encourages us to become at ease with the notion that human knowledge has numerous limitations, raising questions about anything from whether our preconceived notions about psychology are incorrect to the pursuit of understanding what the hell dark matter is.

Aadi Golchha, a writer and commentator, is the host and producer of the nonpartisan economics podcast *The Economics Review*, which analyses cutting-edge economic research through engaging discussions. Authors, professors, and other top authorities on economics, finance, and public policy are interviewed in this podcast.

Many times, tourists are unaware that automated web data collection techniques laid the groundwork for their preferred fare aggregator and lodging services, including trivago and Sky scanner. Web scraping is a new technology that has ingrained itself into internet users' daily lives despite being completely hidden from view. Web scraping professionals who launched the podcast **OxyCast** explain this enigmatic and interesting technique. **OxyCast**, despite being extremely technical, is an excellent resource for learning about the vast business uses of web scraping, ranging from simple methods of data collecting to complex strategies for maintaining access to real-time information from many sources at once.

Gastropod examines food from a scientific and historical perspective. Every two weeks, co-hosts Cynthia Graber and Nicola Twilley deliver a brand-new episode. The history and science of gum, the coffee bean, the origin of the bouillon cube, and the way food is grown, raised, and processed to become what we eat were some of the earlier themes covered. Field tours are sometimes followed by expert interviews on certain programs.

Throughout most textbooks, women in history are conspicuously absent. The five-minute daily podcast **Encyclopedia Womanica** from **Wonder Media Network** fills in the gaps by showcasing inspirational women. An individual theme, such as indigenous women, troublemakers, or educators, is the centre of each season. Recent episodes explore the stories of

women who are as diverse as R&B singer Aaliyah and suffragist Mary Edwards Walker. **Womanica** is a student-focused podcast that also offers instructors free lesson plans they may use in the classroom. However, anyone can listen to this brief program.

The number one history podcast is **Hardcore History**, hosted by Dan Carlin. Carlin uses a radio drama story-telling technique to engage and immerse listeners in the historical events rather than presenting history as a collection of dry facts. But you won't be able to finish this podcast in a single workout because each episode lasts anywhere from four to six hours, which makes it more like an audio book than a short-form podcast. For a truly in-depth study of historical events, Carlin frequently produces a series of audio episodes devoted to a particular era. For instance, the six-part series "Blueprint for Armageddon" outlines the major World War I events.

Advantages of Podcasting in the Classroom

Asynchronous interactive educational podcasting between teachers and students has a lot of advantages. It is important to recognize the unique synergy between functional advantages like usability and accessibility and educational advantages like the ability to deliver single-concept-themed lectures on the go, condensed reviews or reflections on lecture material, individualized narrative feedback, and gentle guidance to the student. The two most advantageous uses of podcasts in

college classrooms—as brief, single-concept lectures, summaries of narrowly focused material, reviews, and narrative audio feedback to students—are the topic of this essay. (Maher Palenque)

Using podcasting, professors can effortlessly provide interesting audio content that students can access whenever and wherever they are. A student merely needs to sign up for a podcast feed, and you can then send them instructive content instead of waiting for them to arrive. Podcasts are a simple way to engage students and enhance teaching and learning in schools, universities, and institutions. Numerous educational institutions that have introduced podcasting into their curricula have noted success. This can be ascribed to the simplicity with which podcasts can be produced and consumed, as well as to the different ways in which educational podcasts can improve students' learning.

- A. **Circadian availability and flexible learning-** The mobility and accommodation of inculcation podcasts are one of their most astronomically immense benefits. The competency to download podcasts to a mobile contrivance enables the learner to facilely and whenever access the cognition resources. Every smartphone may download free podcast subscription apps, which further simplify the procedure. Apple Podcasts, a top-notch podcast app, is preinstalled on iPhones.
- B. **Podcasts can be made private-** If one wants to make a podcast that is

only available to his or her pupils and no one else; there is withal the option to make it private. Here, all the same rules apply; all that is required to give everyone access to the content is to issue them a special link or password.

- C. **Students heedfully auricular discern more often than they visually examine or read something-** The attention that podcasting draws is one of its greatest strengths. It can be arduous to persuade students to read an article or watch a recorded lecture for 30 minutes. This is due to the fact that text and video require the student to pay close attention and sit still while concentrating on a single task. This is tough, as most people are cognizant, not the least of which is the variety of diversions that are simply waiting on the next internet tab.
- D. **Content Engendered by Students-** The conception of student-engendered material or active learning activities is one of the most fascinating and worthwhile utilizations of podcasting in edification. Edifiers frequently let their students make their own podcasts, which may contain questions, conversations, presentations, or projects. Then, their classmates could get access to these. This promotes engagement with the subject matter and gives students the opportunity to take charge of a portion of their

inculcation. They can make suggestions, offer opinions, and impart erudition to one another.

E. **Podcasting in Inculcation: A Review of the Lecture-**

The simplest application of podcasting is to capture subsisting lectures. Students can now expeditiously access them, engendering priceless study implements. The podcast can be utilized by students as a study avail or to get yare for future tests. Anyone who struggled to understand a subject in class is welcome to heedfully aurally perceive this podcast. They are in liberty to learn the material and comprehend the subject at their own pace. The faculty to study material perpetually is very subsidiary for pupils from diverse cultural backgrounds or those who struggle with learning. Conclusively, as antecedently verbally expressed, it can be arduous to persuade students to view an hour-prolix lecture video. Instead, provide them with audio so they may heedfully aurally perceive it while performing their responsibilities.

F. **Compensate for Missed Classes:**

Students don't always skip classes out of sloth. By providing a podcast, one is infelicitous since a sick student who has missed numerous classes can now download lectures that have already been given. They can consequently fill in the gaps as a result. An edifier can withal record the lecture as a podcast if they are

unable to attend their classes for a fortnight. This fills in for any missed lectures by being made available to the students.

G. **Experience of Students over**

Time- A pedagoga or preceptor might use lecture recordings to avail them ascertain they always present a subject in the best way possible. This is utilizable when the pedagoga in question conducts the same course throughout the course of numerous sessions. The preceptor can then ascertain that the curriculum is covered evenly and that each student has the same experience and erudition.

H. **Edification Podcasting: Keeping Students Current**

- It's not compulsory for podcasts in inculcation to be about lectures and edifications. The administrative branch of colleges, universities, and schools may withal utilize it. A podcast could be acclimated to verbalize about school news or to remind students to consummate the most recent form. A podcast may accommodate as a more efficacious reminder than an electronic mail, which is frequently read expeditiously and forgotten.

I. **Advantages for Visual and Noetic Impairments-**

Learning through listening is disputably one of the best pedagogical features that edifying podcasting offers. Learning through heedfully aurally perceiving is more pleasurable and less tiresome than reading, according to

many members of the present student population. The lure of inculcative podcasts may persuade reluctant readers to pick up the book. Podcasts can be an immensely colossal avail to students who struggle with reading due to phrenic disabilities like dyslexia. When a visual handicap makes standard learning techniques arduous, podcasts might be just as auxiliary.

J. **Language Learning-** Learning incipient languages is one of the most prevalent utilizations of scholastic podcasting. Any podcast listener may locate a broadcast that is edifying any language they optate to learn and expeditiously pick it up. This kind of edifying podcast is frequently engendered in a "bite-sized" format, with the conception that we will learn one phrase or even one word in each episode.

K. In research from Gunderson and Cumming, it is stated that the **Universal Design for Learning (UDL)** framework for accessible course design and delivery is being adopted by several universities. The use of audio podcasts as a teaching tool gives students alternatives for involvement, representation, and expression while also aligning with the three UDL criteria. (Gunderson and Cumming)

Disadvantages and Cautions

While there are several advantages to podcasts and podcasting, disadvantages are also present. As has already been stated, the goal of podcasting is to make audio files

available to a larger audience and disseminate them on a global scale. Its instructional purpose is to enhance a new collaborative aspect where students can freely and creatively add to and listen to numerous themes. However, podcasts are occasionally targeted by vandalism just like wikis and blogs, which degrades their accuracy and quality. The free-form nature of podcasting has a double implication: while it certainly makes it simple to download and upload audio and video files, it also makes it simple for anyone to copy protected content without the owners' consent and to add deceptive or inappropriate content on an open and collaborative Web.

Not all teachers have the same level of technological proficiency as pupils have. It is just as beneficial to allow teacher candidates to use these technological tools for learning as it is for actual pupils. Teachers gain exposure to cutting-edge technology while seeing firsthand the advantages and drawbacks of podcasts in a classroom setting. The use of podcasts in teacher preparation programs allowed applicants to learn new pedagogical concepts in addition to improving their proficiency with the course material. They can pick up a different teaching approach to use in their classes, learning a new skill in the process.

Teachers can use podcasting as a valuable resource to help students learn and teach languages. It is an alternate teaching strategy that can help you develop better listening abilities. The majority of podcast creators are teachers who utilize this

technology to interact with their students outside of the regular classroom. Podcasting is a technology that enables teachers to share their thoughts and recommendations for enhancing their teaching style. But it's crucial to pick relevant material. Because kids typically don't take notes and always remember what they hear, it is advisable to steer clear of difficult content that contains several images and details. Not conveying too much information in a single podcast is crucial because students might not be able to absorb all the messages in a single podcast, it's crucial to avoid communicating too much information at once. Teachers must select the key ideas and guide pupils in understanding them by providing examples and stories.

Each podcast that teachers produce must have an instructional goal and purpose. The most crucial objectives include preparing pupils for new learning, putting out and explaining a hard subject, and offering some alternate methods for comprehending new material. Teachers must use interviews, dialogues, or monologues to explain their material. This is a crucial part because the success or failure of their podcasts depends on the

Impact on India

1. The Indian Podcast Listener Statistics in 2018 found that among all Indians who listen to podcasts, 77 percent do so on their phones, mostly while commuting.

Technology always has an impact on every sector, and inculcation is no exception. Incipient technologies like AI and ML have already made their way into edification and are transforming how we impart inculcation. Artificial Intelligence has helped us make education an immersive

experience and help students understand and learn like never before. AI-powered tools are making education and learning more personalized to suit the student's abilities and come up techniques best suited for the student.

India's diversity and the vigorous affection and ardency its people have for their native tongue make up one of its most distinctive characteristics. Initially solely available in English, podcasts are now available in a number of regional languages, including Gujarati, Marathi, and Hindi. Tamil, among many others As a result, podcasts now have a wider audience across the diverse country.

According to statistics from 2018, 77 percent of Indians who listen to podcasts do so on their cell phones, primarily while driving to and from work (Anand). Today's consumers prefer listening to podcasts because they are accessible and supplementally offer a wide range of diversified content ranging from news, cookery shows, politics, comedy, mythology, drama, and more. This is because the circadian commute takes a paramount duration from their quotidian lives. Material that can be accessed "on the go" in a seamless and non-intrusive manner is just as paramount nowadays as regaling and germane content.

The country's ascending podcast listenership has been further aggravated by the pandemic time and the lockdowns.

Several paramount media and social media players have amended their podcasting strategies during the past years. Despite ranking significantly lower on a per capita substructure than China and the US, India is the third-most immensely colossal podcast listening market in the world, according to a PwC analysis. The number of listeners is expected to expand throughout the projection period at a 34.5 percent CAGR, reaching 17.61 crores by 2023. According to the survey, there were 40 million podcast listeners in India as of the cessation of 2018, up from 25.4 million at the same time in 2017.(PricewaterhouseCoopers)

Podcasts and Indian Education Sector

When one considers that India has always been sizably voluminous in audio listening, dating back to the *Prasar Bharti* days, podcasts only seem to make sense as a natural development from the democratization of internet consumption made possible by telecom carriers like Jio. The ingress of businesses like Spotify has only incremented the exhilaration in this industry and corroborated that international players are cognizant of the development potential of the Indian market.

The medium of podcasts has tapped into this expeditiously expanding market. The pristine concentration of podcasts was on English-language content, but they now provide information in regionally popular Indian languages like Hindi, Telugu, Marathi, Tamil, Punjabi, Bengali, Assamese, Rajasthani, and Bhojpuri. Supplementally, podcasts provide content that appeal to every age group and every mood, including mythological series and bhajans for senior denizens, series that are keenly intellectual and incentivizing for millennials, and kid-convivial stories and poems. The variety of topics covered by podcasts is virtually illimitable, including news, sports, regalement, music, politics, skills, and even general perspectives on life. Consequently, podcasts are gaining popularity as a medium for everyone with a variety of content for demographics that are fluctuating.

Technology use and integration is the focus of the **New Education Policy** (NEP) 2020 vision, which aims to provide learners with a road map for transforming their nation into a globally competitive knowledge economy. A growing kind of online connectivity is podcasting. Education institutions all around India were forced to close down for an indefinite period as a result of the lockdown that was imposed on March 25, 2020. The government and educational institutions reacted quickly, switching the manner of instruction from offline to online. Podcasts were successfully implemented in several educational institutions. In many cases, video lectures supplemented with audio

podcasts enhanced student performances. **Pratham**, India's leading NGO in the space of elementary education, has been playing an active role during this pandemic to connect with students and communities across the country and partner with governments to support learning.

The educational landscape in India saw a sea change as a result of Covid-19. It has advanced even though it has presented several difficulties and chances. To address the Covid-19 situation at hand, the Indian government and various education participants have talked about the potential for e-learning by implementing various digital technologies. India is not fully equipped to use digital platforms to spread education throughout the entire country. Universities and the Indian government are working tirelessly to create a remedy for the country's educational system. Priority should be given to using digital technology to make a statement that will benefit the millions of young pupils in India.

Some good Indian educational Podcasts

1. **Spotify's 'Mission ISRO'**- A nation's sense of itself is predicated on an adroitly engendered myth that contains threads of authenticity, desire, fact, and notion, with the interpretation being shaped by current politics. Ergo, the work of a historian, journalist, or archivist is always arduous. The goal of a critical science historian is to place science in its historical context within the chaotic convivial, cultural, economic, and political

environment. The purport is to humanize the tales and draw attention to the intricate web of relationships that render some events likely while truncating the likelihood of others. The series, which is narrated by Harsha Bhogle, hits the ideal balance between the technical, the gregarious, and of course, the political to provide fascinating storytelling. One story that has infrequently been tinged with romanticism is that of India's space program. It has all the makings of a good drama: an adolescent, scrappy, unfathomably underprivileged nation pushed to the margins by the affluent and potent on the international stage; sassy adolescent scientists with vision and zeal; tenacious, determined engineers who want nothing more than to prosper; a geopolitical environment that necessitates deft negotiation. All of these are amalgamated in the 12-part Spotify pristine series Mission ISRO, which utilizes a variety of interviews and archive material from governmental, journalistic, and academic sources to tell the history of India's space program.

2. **Technology, Together by IIIT Bangalore**- Research centres, programs, and domains that assemble experts in engineering, politics, public administration, political science, sociology, economics, and many other fields have been housed at IIIT Bangalore.

"Technology, Together," a podcast series that delves deep into the intricate world of technology while critically engaging with gregarious, political, and cultural variables that influence the design, engenderment, and utilization of technologies, as a way to celebrate this varied research culture.

3. **The Intersection**- This podcast demonstrates how science, culture, and history intersect in India for all culture vultures and science nerds out there. Every fortnight, journalists Samanth Subramanian and Padmaparna Ghosh engender an edifying episode utilizing a coalescence of their research, interviewing, ingenious cerebrating, and eloquent faculties. Here, one can rediscover the consequentiality of culture.
4. **The History of India Podcast** - Since its launch in July 2015, The History of India Podcast has relinquished around 60 episodes across five seasons, in additament to 41 special episodes. The podcast moves through the years in a leisurely manner, pausing for elongated periods to explore not just the key events but the art, architecture, culture, and governmental administration of each era. It commences with a concise explication of "The 16 great households of ancient India," around 600 BC. For instance, in season 2, Patrick interrupts the Kushans' story to discuss "Women, Law, and

Life"—just one of the 11 special programs that season. The lengthy episodes of the podcast contain enough variety in material and tone to keep one heedfully listening albeit it relies on a single voice (Kit Patrick) for narration. Without bombarding the spectator with dates and events, the episodes manage to be dense with detail.

5. **KabhiSocha Hai** - Kids can listen to the factual science podcast **KabhiSocha Hai**. Each episode lasts between three and four minutes, during which we tackle a fascinating subject head-on and offer a clear, kid-convivial explication predicated on logic and/or science. This edifying podcast, which is distributed in Hindi and some English, is intended not just for children but additionally for any curious adults who would relish brushing up on their erudition of science fundamentals in order to appear well-apprised when children ask them these kinds of questions.
6. **The Life of Science**- It commenced as a blog in 2016, a side project of two freelance science heralds AashimaFreidog and NanditaJayaraj, who chronicled the lives of the women scientists they encountered while travelling between Indian labs and research facilities. Since then, the project has gained a lot more support. The zealously project, which was born out of the desire to visually perceive

and aurally perceive femme stories from Indian science in the media, has developed into a collective composed of a flexible team and a growing network of freelancers, which now includes science communicators, scientists, graduate students, journalists, artists, and engenderers of multimedia content. It is an efficacious technique to show adolescent people the achievements of some of our nation's most well-kenned scientists while additionally exhibiting girls what they are capable of.

7. **India Classified**- When information is restricted by the regime so that it is not available to everyone, this is referred to as relegation. In the majority of nations, relegation is accomplished by categorizing the regime's data according to sundry levels of sensitivity. The relegation process is often done in the following order: top secret, secret, confidential, restricted, and declassified. An exhaustive background inquiry is indispensable when handling relegated information. The mechanism of access to information is hierarchical. All information will be accessible to the top official, while access to information at lower calibers of the hierarchy will decline.
8. The podcast **India Classified** explores India's hidden secrets and debunks certain common beliefs. While exploring the idea that "Not

everything is as it seems," the program maintains a scientific outlook. Learn more about the untold reality behind traditions, superstitions, prevailing views, the design of historic temples, and much more.

Conclusion

Every industry is impacted by technology, and edification is no different. The way we distribute edification is transmuting as a result of incipient technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning that have already made their way into the sector. India has a growing number of individuals who are connected to the cyber world, with an immensely colossal chunk of its population having access to smart phones and regularly listen to podcasts. Podcasts have developed groups of like-minded people, given listeners a sense of community, and provided a venue for interaction and the sharing of interests.

In order to implement the courses and best prepare their students for this changing world, Indian universities should develop more sophisticated technologies. To achieve the main objective, they must offer a model of learning and teaching that is ever more advanced, with authentic assessments, personal lifetime learning, face-to-face delivery combined with technology in a multi-model delivery format.

For the educational institution to be prepared to deal with any future pandemic circumstances, they need to support its

knowledge and IT infrastructure. India should adopt more creative measures to guarantee that all kids have practical access to education during any pandemic like situation. E-learning practices should continue to benefit pupils greatly and podcasts can be of great use along with other options.

References:

- Anand, Gautam Raj. "2019 Will Be a Terrific Year for Podcasts in India – Here's Why." *YourStory.com*, 5 Sept. 2019, yourstory.com/2019/01/2019-terrific-year-podcasts-india/amp.
- Berry, Richard. "Podcast Studies." *Richard Berry*, 2 Jan. 2020, richardberry.eu/podcast-studies.
- Gunderson, Jamie L., and Therese M. Cumming. "Podcasting in Higher Education as a Component of Universal Design for Learning: A Systematic Review of the Literature." *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, Informa UK Limited, May 2022, pp. 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2022.2075430>.
- Wikipedia contributors. "History of Podcasting." *Wikipedia*, 23 Sept. 2022, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_podcasting.
- Meng, P. (2005). Podcasting and Vodcasting: A white paper. http://edmarketing.apple.com/adcsintitute/wp-content/Missouri_Podcasting_White_Paper.pdf. Accessed October 7, 2022.

Maher Palenque, Stephanie. "The Power of Podcasting: Perspectives on Pedagogy." *Journal of Instructional Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, Grand Canyon University, Aug. 2016, pp. 4–7.

<https://doi.org/10.9743/jir.2016.1>.

Price water house Coopers. "India's Entertainment and Media Industry to Clock Over INR 451,373Cr by 2023: PwC Report." PwC, www.pwc.in/press-releases/2019/global-entertainment-and-media-outlook-2019-2023.html. Accessed 14 Oct. 2022.

Townsend Gard, Elizabeth and Voge, Colette, Podcasting for Corporations and Universities: Look Before You Leap. *Journal of Internet Law*,

Forthcoming, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=995059>

Image Sources

1. <https://www.bookwidgets.com/blog/2021/09/7-ideas-to-get-your-students-excited-about-podcasts-the-podcast-guide-for-teachers>
2. <https://www.thepodcasthost.com/equipment/podcast-equipment-guide/>
3. <https://www.freepik.com/free-photos-vectors/podcast>
4. <https://www.epraves.com/blog/podcast-in-education/>
5. <https://bestmediainfo.com/2022/07/there-will-be-900-million-internet-users-in-india-by-2025-led-by-rural-growth-iamai-kantar-report>

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